

AFFECTIVENESS AND ITS IMPLICATIONS IN COGNITIVE DEVELOPMENT PROCESSES

 DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7916604

Liliane Rodrigues de Araújo

Pedagogue. Psychopedagogue. Postdoctoral in Social Psychology. Scientific Consultant.

Email: srgrodriguesdesouza@gmail.com.

Sérgio Rodrigues de Souza

Pedagogue. Master in Education. Education Specialist (Pedagogue) at the Espírito Santo

State Department of Education. Email: liliaraujoe10@hotmail.com.

Cleidimar Rosalino Pereira

Pedagogue. Master in Education. PhD student in Pedagogical Sciences at the University of

Pedagogical Sciences “Enrique José Varona” - Ciudad Libertad - Havana (Cu). Email:

cleiderosalino@hotmail.com.

José Luis Gotay Sardines

Doctor in Pedagogical Sciences. Full Professor at the University of Pedagogical Sciences

“Enrique José Varona” - Ciudad Libertad - Havana (Cu).

ABSTRACT

This scientific article deals with affectivity and its implication in cognitive development processes. Its scientific relevance lies in the fact that it contributes to the academic world by expanding scientific knowledge about human nature and its relationship with knowledge. Its social relevance lies in presenting to the general public ways of dealing with ways of being and living and how this can help in learning. This is a bibliographical, analytical, descriptive research, using the analytical-synthetic as an investigative method of interpretation. The dialectical approach was used as a general method of science, which integrates the quantitative and qualitative aspects, presenting the relationship between the internal and external aspects of the object, its causes and consequences. The overall objective is to discuss a didactic-pedagogical intervention proposal that fosters the creation of affective bonds between teachers and students, with a view to expanding the students' cognitive potential. Affectivity is a striking element in the conditioning and formation of the cognitive capacity of students, especially those who are in the adolescent development phase, because it is a moment in their lives that needs

recognition and support from those who are caring for them of their preparation for the life that lies ahead of them and for which they do not feel secure enough.

Keywords: affectivity. Teachers. Students. Educational conflicts.

INTRODUCTION

Affectivity is a striking element in the conditioning and formation of the cognitive capacity of students, especially those who are in the adolescent development phase, because it is a moment in their lives that needs recognition and support from those who are caring for them. of their preparation for the life that lies ahead of them and for which they do not feel secure enough.

When professors and tutors dedicate their time, in addition to teaching the syllabus, also to listen to their students about their intrinsic difficulties, in a way that does not constitute a deviation from their statutory functions, but which are within the scope of their didactic actions -pedagogical, it can be noted that there are advances in the processes of motivation for the objectives set for the formal disciplines, considering that what is intended with formal education is that the student overcomes his difficulties of all kinds, and this includes the more subjective ones, which are part of his private life.

This is a task that falls to the school pedagogical team, as an entity that has assumed the social commitment to fully train the human individual under its tutelage, that is, it is not only up to the idea of transforming the student into a potential genius , it is necessary to *make* him a *man indeed* . And such a thing cannot be achieved in isolation from the processes of linking affectivity to teaching programs and content training, leaving the school with the duty to assume the responsibility of educating within parameters of affectivity.

The human being is a being that reacts according to the situation, therefore, if students are treated well, most of them will seek to treat their teachers and other school employees with the same deference, as well as being able to deepen their systematic studies independently, in search of more effective results for their own lives outside the school walls.

The proposal is not to make the school a welcoming place; it is to think about it from the perspective of coping with the problems that invade it and that, so far, the proposals for solutions presented have proved to be innocuous, because they were thought of in the absence of an element that could add greater value to the methodological and didactic procedures that is used in the execution of educational tasks. This is what we propose here, the rigorous study of affectivity as a means-activity, with the purpose of bringing together the parties involved in

the educational process, enabling the construction of chains of thought that one and do not distance the actors of education (teachers and students) and promote the desired success that is necessary.

AFFECTIVENESS AND ITS IMPLICATIONS IN COGNITIVE DEVELOPMENT PROCESSES

The teacher-student relationship must always be permeated by affectivity, because this represents an extra effort in the search for practicality, effectiveness and efficiency in preparing the student for life, in a redefinition of the teaching-learning process. Each professional must have clearly defined their role in this social context, where this relationship considered here becomes the subject of research, in the search for dialogue, free debate of ideas, social interaction and the decrease in the importance of individualized work. In this new educational paradigm, teacher-student interaction goes beyond professional, school, school year and semester limits. It is, in fact, a relationship that leaves marks, and which must always seek affection and dialogue as a way of building the school space.

Teachers should value students more, that is, emphasis on the student and not on the subject as we are doing. It is important to mention that this does not mean that the teacher will abandon their contents, because only those teachers who have reached a high degree of knowledge about their contents are able to free themselves from them, to effectively give due attention to the real needs. of your students. The teacher should value his student by allowing him to advance in his journey of learning, where he builds and rebuilds, elaborates and re-elaborates his knowledge according to his ability and rhythm and, in this context, the use of networks can expand and implement the teaching and learning process. Without the intrinsic support of the teacher, the student becomes increasingly disinterested and unmotivated. There are many conceptual flaws that have been proposed over time, however what the school has to rescue is its main function which justifies its existence: the function of teaching.

Bruno Bettelheim (2007, p. 28) wrote that

Today , as in the past, the most important and also the most difficult task in raising a child is to help him find meaning in life. Many experiences are needed to achieve this. The child, as he develops, must learn step by step to understand himself better; with this he becomes better able to understand others, and eventually can relate to them in a mutually satisfying and meaningful way. To find deeper meaning, we must be able to transcend the narrow confines of a self-centered existence and believe that we will make a meaningful contribution to life—if not immediately now, then at some future

time. This feeling is necessary so that a person can be satisfied with himself and with what he is doing. In order not to be at the mercy of life's hazards, we must develop our inner resources, so that our emotions, imagination and intellect help and enrich each other. Our positive feelings give us strength to develop our rationality, only hope for the future can sustain us in the adversities that we inevitably encounter.

It is understood from this statement that it is up to teachers and tutors to provide the necessary support so that students can overcome their difficulties in gaining knowledge and much more than that, so that they can overcome, with autonomy, the challenges of passing an existential phase the other.

School life is, in a direct/or indirect way, opaque to the student, seeming and, without any modesty, showing itself to be innocuous, because in the traditional model of education, reduced to the repetitive reductionist theorizing discourse, all possibility of achieving factual knowledge is postponed to the future, taking the obligation of such action out of his responsibility, and only after 15 (fifteen) years or more will the student discover that he has been lied to throughout an existence that is almost an entire generation . In this way, there is no way to create an affective bond with something that will prove to be a farce, in this same future in which it promises to reveal itself as prophetic, that is, the entire school discourse is a ridiculous extension of a profession of faith and , for human beings to build their intelligence through the expression of their creativity, they need experience, to have contact with reality and understand that its manifestation goes far beyond a perspective.

The teacher-student relationship is a field of light and shadow, alternating with each variation of the process to be achieved. And, as much as one can talk about affectivity, which is a real expression of affection, that is, what happens as individuals relate to each other, the big mistake made is that of believing that only pure feelings and held by society , as nobles are part of the set. It begins that, without uncertainties, without insecurities and without aversion towards someone, in particular, there is no way to build bonds of affection with anyone and, this figure, in the conception of Aristotle (799-737 a. H.) would be a god or an animal, because only these two categories can live isolated and deprived of any feeling towards them (Id., 2007). However, the Stagirite is wrong and, throughout history, what has been seen, through the myths of different societies, were the gods approaching humans in search of company, which proves that they also feel isolated and lacking in affection. In the same way, animals form groups, play with each other, defend their peers, which, far from being treated here as an anthropomorphism, is a rudimentary expression of affection.

With regard to school, the horizontal time that the contemporary human spends in this institution gives rise to a very rare type of affectivity, which is the transferential bond of parental responsibility for the figure of the teacher and that, given the unraveling of their own children, assumes this condition, as a compensation factor and neurotic and tragic guilt, for the abandonment of their own.

Based on these explanations, it has been understood that,

The mediation relationships made by the teacher during the pedagogical activities must always be permeated by feelings of welcome, sympathy, respect and appreciation, in addition to understanding, acceptance and appreciation of the other; such feelings not only mark the student's relationship with the object of knowledge, but also affect their self-image, favoring autonomy and strengthening confidence in their abilities and decisions (SILVA and TASSONI, 2004, p. 17).

With this, affectivity can help in deepening the particular construction of the student's personality, making him more capable of breaking with the aspects of learning and appropriation of knowledge.

For Perrenoud (2007, p. 29), "teachers find it difficult to understand what their students do not understand, since they have lost the memory of the path of knowledge, obstacles, uncertainties, shortcuts, moments of intellectual panic or empty." With this, it can be understood that they no longer feel human and are already sure that everything that is preached about the relationship between affectivity and cognition is talk to cover up the students' intellectual disability. And to prove their hypotheses, they compare isolated cases of miserable students, coming from destroyed homes, but who achieved success. They forget the fact that the school is a plural place, formed by contrasts and challenges. And the biggest one is not to lose the sense of humanity and the right balance between what is desirable and what is achievable, *ie.*, between what one is allowed to aim for and what it is possible to achieve, through individual effort.

Understood this narrow existential limit that the school, through its weak speech, tries to make believe that it does not exist; that everything in life is a matter of joint effort and that, with love, affection and respect, all challenges are overcome. The most foolish thing to have as a direction in life is to believe that these three things, all of them created by failures and for failures, can make someone succeed. The will to power is the only means by which previously planned objectives are achieved. When one speaks of affectivity, he is referring to the expression of common feelings of the species, aimed in particular at children who, without this care, cannot feel safe enough to advance to higher levels of existence and, because of this ,

refuse, in an automatic and consequential way, to seek ways of learning. To learn it is necessary to feel safe; therefore, affectivity can be understood as a variant ¹¹used to express security.

TEACHING AS A PEDAGOGICAL SUPPORT

The didactic process, when well conducted, is fundamental in all types of relationships built between thinking beings; above all, with regard to the complex teacher x student relationship which, by nature, is marked by deep and extensive contradictions.

The evidence referring to the influence of extracurricular variables on the regular continuation of the school career, therefore, no longer allow the school to be thought of in terms of an ideal student or an undifferentiated population. However, attention focused entirely on these aspects can lead to a comfortable passive attitude towards current school systems. It is convenient, by the way, to remember that what is known about the importance of extra-school factors, or about the relative irrelevance of specifically school factors, refers to situations found in societies with certain characteristics and schools of certain types; the schools that exist there: schools that are organized according to certain objectives, employ certain teaching methods and certain criteria for evaluating students.

Although one can imagine that significant changes in the school system, perhaps, hardly, operate without transforming society itself, one cannot calmly expect that certain socio-political transformations produce automatic changes in school orientation and practices (MATURANA 2002).

What the author seeks to affirm is that changes in political thought affect the school and all its ideology; however, this takes a considerable amount of time to be absorbed into their curriculum and transferred to students as a mechanism for intellectual construction, for the simple fact that there is [*and always will be*] resistance on the part of the members of that community. School is a place of fierce, heavy disputes, conflicts of all orders and the idea that everyone is equal, everyone is part of the same block of passion is a false discourse that does not convince anyone of its utopian illusion.

Treating the school and teachers as responsible for the success or failure of a student is to cast a task that is familiar and individual onto others; from anyone else. The relationships between teachers and students, within a school environment, are marked by formality and ethics. Once again, it portrays that affectivity is a condition of psychological security necessary

¹¹Variants “are ways of saying the same thing in the same context and with the same truth value.” TARALLO, F. *Sociolinguistic research*. 5. Ed. Sao Paulo: Attica, 1997.

for children, in particular and, later, it extends to the adult human being, given the ontogenetic formation of gender.

The failure or success of the child, according to Ferreiro & Teberosky (1996), depends among other things:

[...] The conditions in which the child is at the time of receiving education. Those who are in very advanced moments of conceptualization are the only ones who can take advantage of traditional teaching and are the ones who learn what the teacher proposes to teach them. The rest are those who fail whom the school accuses of being unable to learn or of 'learning difficulties', according to a now classic terminology (p. 277).

What the authors are dealing with is that education professionals lack knowledge about the human developmental stages, especially with regard to cognitive maturation, making them able to enter the field of scientific learning. Once again, it must be emphasized that the speech of love and affection does not problematize, nor does it solve issues related to learning. When a teacher, technically unprepared, tries to teach things to a group of children and *fails* in the task, accusations happen from all sides, in which he blames the family and the social conditions of the students for the result and the school and some *colleagues*, also lacking of pedagogical knowledge accuse the aforementioned teacher of not having empathy, of being didactic, that his posture causes fear in children and, for this simple reason, not learning.

In the midst of all this confusion, which does not add anything to scientific knowledge, because, as a rule, they do not dominate anything in the field of science, there is an affectivity factor, and the fear expressed is not in direct relation to the teacher; rather, a primitive feeling that failure may result in severe sanctions, such as abandonment, by adults. It is a complex game, in which the need for patience, care in approaching the problem with the families, offering support and understanding are crucial elements for overcoming the problem situation; however, it is not enough to solve it.

Affectivity cannot be treated as a feeling that can be manipulated according to the political-ideological interest of a group that took for itself the messianic idea that they have magic formulas to save humanity from all evils and, with this, distorted the components of institutions and elements that came to be transformed into auxiliary components of pedagogy. The human being is a being who can learn anything, and for that, there is a need for commitment and a great deal of emotional and intellectual effort, which will revert to the creative capacity, generating, through his creative commitment, products and ideas that are useful to society. .

Throughout this process, you need to be motivated, to receive enthusiasm from those around you, especially your teachers and mentors. All this represents processes of affectivity

being directed towards the transformation of the autonomous individual into an independent individual, something that one wants to deny and even destroy, in the name of an ideal of a utopian society. What most of these ideologues disguised as educational consultants and a majority of teachers without any technical preparation aim for is not an ideal of affectivity applied to educational procedures; it is a tyranny that turns all students, without distinction, into eunuchs, in all fields of human existence.

In this regard, Piaget (1989) writes that,

It is impossible to find a behavior that comes only from affectivity, without any cognitive element. It is also impossible to find a behavior composed only of cognitive elements... Although affective and cognitive factors are inseparable in a given behavior, they seem to be different in nature... It is obvious that affective factors are involved even in the most subtle ways. abstract intelligence. For a student to solve an algebra problem or for a mathematician to discover a theorem, there must be an intrinsic interest, an extrinsic interest, or a starting need. While working, states of pleasure, disappointment, anxiety as well as feelings of fatigue, exertion, annoyance, etc., come into play. When finishing the work, feelings of success or failure may occur; and, finally, the student can experience aesthetic feelings flowing from the coherence of his solution (pp. 22-23).

It can be seen that affectivity alone is not a guarantee that the student will develop in all the aspects that will make it possible to advance to the next grade, even though affectivity and cognition have a close relationship, both complement each other and can, together, assist in learning acquisition. If a child who does not receive affection from the family, upon arriving at school is surrounded by care and affection and therefore begins to socialize productively with other classmates, the tendency is that he will be able to produce and build a series of valuable concepts about oneself and human relationships, being able, obviously, to also extract the knowledge arising from this relationship; however, this is not enough to guarantee that he develops all his abilities at the same time as other children who have not faced the same affective challenge.

Over time, social demands have become more and more complex, demanding from the school a complete curriculum, in which the objectives of leading the student to conquer a place in the labor market and at the same time make him a virtuous, conscious, critical and active individual, capable of dealing with the most complex issues that life imposes on him. This made educators find themselves in the midst of a whirlwind of demands that were passed on to them; but, which, contrary to the Herculean requirement, were not instrumentalized, since the school dressed in a new costume; but its archaic personological structure remains the same and, to make matters worse, the bureaucrats who implemented the series of changes in the school

curricula do not know how to do it, do not know how to teach it and did not develop instruments that allow the empirical evaluation of the processes applied.

EDUCATION AND ITS RELATION WITH THE EXISTENCE

Education and life are phenomena that are directly related; considering that at birth the individual is inserted, in an immediate way, in an educational process. In principle, he will be submitted to non-formal education, carried out by his family and the group to which he belongs; then he will go to school, where his previous knowledge will be organized in a methodical way and his behavior will undergo a series of transformations, more or less radical.

In this sense, it is important to emphasize that the educational process does not end in a certain period of human life; it takes on new meanings at each stage the human being goes through. Thus, as long as there is life, there will be someone educating and being educated, because man is always subjecting his knowledge to experiences and the results of these need to be analyzed, interpreted and synthesized, which, therefore, will remain in full force. all the fullness of being that submits to the process.

It is evident that, in order to be valid, education must correspond to the aspirations of those who will submit to it, not just the aspirations; but, above all, the cultural characteristics of the environment in which the individual is inserted, under penalty of making something empty of meaning, or it will reflect the way of being of others to the detriment of the individual who is being educated. An education for domination will produce dominated beings and will require the presence of other beings who configure themselves as dominators; on the other hand, when exercised in such a way as to promote the practice of freedom of thought, education will always envision the free man as a whole and, in this education, the domain is exercised by the individual's ability to argue with the other, without, however, taking away from him the right to object.

Linhares (2002) observes that:

Fear, disintegration, violence, the exacerbation of particularisms, the fragmentation of knowledge, technological advances under the command of a late capitalism and aggressions to the environment are – at an accelerated pace – modifying the vital landscape (p. 103) .

Turning attention to this quote, it is observed that the evils of modernity are configured as obstacles for individuals to have access to the educational process, since these evils affect, especially adolescents who are in the process of personality formation, this refers to many the

problems that educators face in classrooms when they try to deal with the issues mentioned, most of the time, they lack the necessary expertise to face the student's fears, as they also have fears ; a fear that leads them to distance themselves from the student, generating conflicts that culminate in acts of violence and vandalism.

It is important to point out that the teacher is not being blamed for the disintegration now established among students and why not say among families, since these also have a share of responsibility in the formation of individuals; what is actually desired is to demonstrate that the problem experienced in the school context cannot be seen only from the point of view of those who are directly involved in the process of transmitting knowledge, bearing in mind that they also present, in most cases, sometimes, the same weaknesses presented by the students.

This observation brings us face to face with one of the greatest contradictions observed in the school context, which refers precisely to the similarity of conflicts between educators and students; the contradictory point resides in the fact that these similarities, instead of bringing them together, end up pushing them apart, as if one could not discover the human being that is inside the other, under penalty of both showing their weaknesses in the face of life.

With regard to these contradictions, Zagury (2006) observes that the modern school, that is, the school inserted in modernity, creates some myths to mask its inability to deal with the existing conflicts in its context, conflicts that occur within it; but, who were not necessarily born within the school; they come from the multiplicity of relationships that are established in all types of coexistence and end up flowing into the school, and then you have to look for a villain to play the role that is imposed on him and which he cannot extricate himself from without falling into disgrace .

It is important to point out that despite seeming contradictory in this discussion, Zagury's thought strengthens the discussion about the dilemmas introduced in the school and also shows quite clearly that the problem cannot be seen only from the point of view of one of the segments of the school. educational action. All those involved must assume their role in transforming a reality that is not favorable to them.

Complementing and, with the intention of illustrating her speech, the author points out four myths that, according to her, were created to mask the ineffectiveness of the school:

Myth 1: The affection and affection of teachers are essential elements for students to learn. The author agrees that affection and affection are essential; however, it does not, by itself, determine learning. He also points out that such a statement leads to the false idea that a serious, introspective teacher, who does not externalize feelings due to personal characteristics, cannot be a good teacher, which is, according to the author, an untruth. Another aspect mentioned is

making the student believe that the teacher who does not prioritize affective relationships with the student, although polite, is a bad teacher (even if he gives wonderful classes). In this context, the author warns, “if the student fails, 'the fault' lies with the teacher, who did not know how to build a good relationship.

Myth 2: With a good teacher, students learn without making any efforts, motivation arises, as well as concentration. Studying or doing chores at home becomes virtually unnecessary. The classes are wonderful that everyone can learn easily. At this point, the author agrees that a well-planned class that uses methodological and audiovisual resources, with intelligent and challenging exercises, is extremely more motivating, speeds up learning, makes learning enjoyable and, in general, the process is facilitated.

Despite such considerations, the author seeks to dispel this myth with the following argument:

I consider it serious harm to make the student and his family believe that, when the teacher acts in a methodologically modern and adequate way, every student learns as if by magic. There will always be, also on the part of the student, the need for dedication and concentration, for moments of individual study to practice what he has studied, to reflect in order to consolidate concepts and transfer learning. 'Selling illusions' of this type only leads the student to think that everything related to learning is the sole and exclusive responsibility of the school and/or the teacher. He doesn't need to make any effort, absolutely nothing, because the 'good classes' do everything for him. Students and families need to believe again and realize that there is always a need for reciprocity. No matter how good the teacher's performance is, it will never eliminate the fact that the student is an active and integral part of the process and that a share of responsibility depends on him/her to be shared with the institution (ZAGURY, 2006, p. 29).

Myth 3: Community participation is essential to the quality of education, the author debunks this myth on the grounds that community participation (family) is important to bring information and learn about the activities that schools carry out, in addition to monitoring of the children's performance and attitudes towards studies. They can cooperate a lot when they provide their impressions and ideas, as well as criticisms and suggestions, however, when such participation takes on an imposing character, of confrontation, manipulation or struggle for power, it can never be considered positive or democratic. It is up to the community to participate, yes, but to strengthen the principles of equal rights, not to impose conditions and never obtain advantages for themselves or their children.

According to Bordieu and Passeron (1989, p. 5), “[...] each family transmits to its children, more indirectly than directly, a certain cultural capital and a certain ethos , a system

of implicit and deeply internalized values , which it helps to define, among other things, activities in relation to cultural capital and the school institution.

Myth 4: If a significant percentage of students have poor results, it means that the teacher has failed, to demystify this statement, it is emphasized that, with good teachers and good infrastructure, the percentage of students with chances to learn and have positive results grows geometrically, even who are discouraged. He goes on to warn that generalization is always dangerous, and in the case in question, the student's previous school life is ignored, poorly developed work in previous grades, which may have left external learning gaps, sometimes not remedied in just one school year ; the family's posture in relation to the school, as well as the willingness of the child or young person to 'do their part', and also, the idea that 'if the teacher teaches, the student learns', considering that, learning and teaching are two interrelated processes, that is, one influences the other, subjects also subject to a range of intervening factors (personal motivation, intellectual capacity, affective perception in relation to certain components of the curriculum, emotional situation of the family). These factors affect both teachers and students (ZAGURY, 2006).

I agree with the author when she postulates that the legitimization of such myths has contributed to many discrepancies when trying to justify the causes of student failure, however, one cannot lose sight of the fact that these justifications are always supported by authorities that in education only understand theoretical character, denying its practicality. Teachers, in turn, end up assimilating this discourse and, aware that such myths are legitimate, end up embracing this discourse, jeopardizing their own convictions of right and wrong.

Considering the many ideologies impregnated in these myths, it is believed that most of them are legitimized within schools and have already been impregnated in the official discourse; educators and students, in turn, end up assimilating it, the former always feeling that they are not doing everything possible and the latter certain that not everything possible was done for them to learn, or pass year, since that is the main objective.

The analysis of these myths also allows one to verify that if, on the one hand, a certain amount of affection is positive as a pedagogical tool; positive is also a certain effort on the part of the student to earn his right to a really quality education, which will not come only through the good will of the teacher.

FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

The issue of affectivity, as a relevant component for Pedagogy, is a subject that has been standing out for a long time and several studies and works have been carried out and published, respectively. In this, in particular, we sought to be more objective and transparent as to what, in fact, it represents in the human existential condition and how it should be seen by education professionals.

When a systematic analysis is proposed about the process of affective development in the school space, linking it to the cognitive mechanisms of learning and teaching, a profound influence of the former on intellectual development is perceived. Piaget (1988) points out that there is a unit that connects affectivity and cognition, defending, with this perception, the need to investigate the interference of the first on human daily actions, more specifically, with regard to dealings with formal education. For him, knowledge is constructed in the interaction between emotion and reason, as he defends the existence of a direct relationship between the broad acquisition of knowledge and feelings of affection. All of this occurs because the teacher-student relationship will be decisive in the learning process, since the influence of the first is, in many cases, decisive on the mood of the second. The more challenges and experiences are made available to students, the more opportunities they have to expand their field of knowledge and theorize based on the discoveries they are making. This makes it possible to create a very close affective bond that becomes permanent.

This is a close relationship that cannot be neglected, under penalty of falling into the redundancy of looking for magic formulas and answers far beyond what supports the actions of the interpersonal relationship between the student and his teacher. Knowing these gaps that are being filled as the school years progress in children's lives is an urgent need. At a certain point in the relationship, there is a certain type of transfer that, if the teacher does not know how to manage it, can cause serious problems. The requirement is that they have full control over the affective processes that can both be a factor in facilitating learning and, to the same extent, can represent a hindrance and a complicating factor in their situation. Many professors are cold in dealing with their students, because in the past, they did not know the right measure of distance in dealing with them and something went very wrong and he, once again, proves that he was not capable of knowing his intrapsychic world, continuing as an individual who is not psychologically resolved, emotionally lacking and thus, prefers to hide behind an iron mask (SOUZA and MÁRIO, 2019).

In an attempt to solve problems that are beyond its scope, the contemporary school creates myths involving creativity and, over time, takes these same fables that it itself created, in order to hide its incompetence, as unquestionable and irrefutable truths.

BIBLIOGRAPHIC REFERENCES

ARISTOTLE. *The politics*. São Paulo: Escala, 2007.

BETELHEIM, B. *The Psychoanalysis of Fairy Tales*. 21. Ed. São Paulo: Paz e Terra, 2007.

BOURDIEU, P.; PASSERON, J.-C. *Reproduction: elements for a theory of the education system*. São Paulo: Francisco Alves, 1989.

FERREIRO, E.; TEBEROSKY, A. *Psychogenesis of written language*. Porto Alegre: Medical Arts, 1996.

LINHARES, C.; LEAL, MC; MONTEIRO, AJJ (eds.). *Teacher training: a critique of hegemonic reason and politics*. Rio de Janeiro: DP&A, 2002.

MATURANA, RH *Emotions and language in education and politics*. 3. Ed. Belo Horizonte: UFMG, 2002.

PERRENOUD, P. *10 New Skills for Teaching* . Porto Alegre: Artmed, 2007.

1 PIAGET, J. Psychology of early childhood. In : KATZ, David. *Psychology of ages*. São Paulo: Manole, 1988.

PIAGET, J. *The child's language and thought*. 5. Ed. São Paulo: Martins Fontes, 1989.

SILVA, SA; TASSONI, ECM *Affectivity in the Classroom*. Rio de Janeiro: Voices, 2004.

SOUZA, SR; MÁRIO, JCM *A Study on Emotion and Intellectual Learning*. Vitória: JRPRINT Ltda, 2014.

SOUZA, SR *Affectivity and its implication in children's cognitive processes*. São Paulo: PerSe, 2018.

ZAGURY, T. *The hostage teacher: for parents and teachers to understand why education fails in Brazil*. Rio de Janeiro: Record, 2006.